

AN APPLICATION OF LINEAR DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS IN THE DESIGN OF INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM (LINEAR DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS & INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM)

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ABSTRACT

Background and objective:

Intrusion Detection Systems essentially involve processing of high dimensional network data using various multivariate statistical methods. In this work the Intrusion detection systems designed for network features and non-network features are compared for their efficiency.

Materials and Methods:

This current work has used Linear Discriminant Method to analyze the network data in the design of Intrusion Detection System by applying it to the network attacks from UNSW-NB15 intrusion detection data along with MITRE ATT&CK framework. The Linear Discriminant Method is applied the trained data set to build the model and also to test data set to validate the model. Separate models were built for connection features and non-connection features.

Results:

The performance measures are deduced using Confusion Matrix for the models. The results indicate that network features are best suited to detect cyber intrusions as compared to the other network features.

Conclusion:

The network features of the computer system coupled with balanced training dataset and test data set shows improvement in the efficiency of the intrusion detection system.

Keywords: Intrusion Detection System, Linear Discriminant Analysis, Network features, Connection features, Intrusion Categories, Cyber security.

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INTRODUCTION

In the past few decades computer scientists have come up with sophisticated tools and policies to safeguard the interests of legitimate users of the networks by ensuring the confidentiality of their data¹. In spite of such developments malicious users identify various network vulnerabilities to gain unauthorized access in to the system for financial gain, political advantage and spy on competitors to have an unfair advantage. Therefore, the situation demands continuous development and updating of existing intrusion detection systems to keep in pace with improved technologies and sophisticated cyber-attacks². Responding to the recent developments in the cyber security scenario researchers have carried out extensive works to develop various real time intrusion detection systems (IDS) to enhance the network security to legitimate users^{3,4,5}.

In the design of such intrusion detection systems the statistical methods, specifically that correspond to multivariate analysis have become very crucial in the analysis and design of such systems^{3,6}. Besides, there is a need to test the efficiency of the designed intrusion systems and consequently an appropriate network data set becomes a basic requirement to analyze, design and test those systems⁷. Investigators have used different kinds of data sets that varied in features, mode of attacks on network systems, and the number of features depending on the availability and compatibility with their research. A work on Detection and Visualization of Computer Network Attacks using Principal Component Analysis has employed 1998 DARPA data set while a few other works on feature selection for intrusion detection system has used KDD CUP 99 data set^{7,8,9,10,11,12}.

My current study to design intrusion detection system has employed multivariable method known as Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA). Many earlier research works also have used LDA in the design of intrusion detection systems. An intrusion detection system that has used LDA with mahalanobis distance found to be very effective in the separation of intrusions from the normal behavior¹³. Another study on KDD Cup99 attack data set that used LDA for feature reduction found that the classifications of intrusions were done with minimum error rate as compared to other classification methods¹⁴.

This study has used UNSW-NB15 data set along with Linear Discriminant Analysis to design the intrusion detection system. As far as I know there were no earlier studies on UNSW-NB15 that has used LDA model to design an intrusion system. This study will also identify attributes (items related to basic features and content features of the network) and connection features that efficiently predict various intrusion categories and compare attributes and connection features efficiency in identifying intrusion detection.

Description of UNSW-NB15 dataset

The UNSW-NB15 data set has been created by the cyber security research group at the Australian Center for Cyber Security in an effort to update and remove the shortcomings in the other existing popular network intrusion datasets such as DARPA, KDD98, KDDCUP99 and NSLKDD. First and foremost reason for creating the UNSW-NB15 dataset is that these existing datasets were over 10 years old and incapable of identifying

sophisticated modern network intrusions. Further, these datasets have a large number of redundant records in the training dataset and missing records that greatly affected the nature of the data¹⁵. Though, several of these shortcomings were addressed in the updated datasets, it lacked the representation of the modern attack environment.

The UNSW-NB15 data set contains records of normal categories and various attack categories. The Normal categories are authenticated inflow of data with 2218761 records. In the attack categories the Generic has highest number with 215481 records followed by Exploits, Fuzzers, Denial-of-Service and Reconnaissance categories with records 44525, 24246, 16353 and 13987 respectively. The remaining attack categories Analysis, Backdoors, Shell Code and Worms have few records with 2677, 2329, 1511 and 174 records respectively.

VARIABLES USED IN THE MODEL

The connection feature variables are derived variables from type of service, number of connections having different combinations of source address, destination address, source port and destination port in the last 100 connections according to the last time. The variables are as follows:

- Number of connections that contain the same service http, ftp, ssh, dns etc., and source IP address.
- Number of connections that contain the same service http, ftp, ssh, dns etc., and destination IP address.
- Number of connections of the same destination IP address.
- Number of connections of the same source IP address.
- Number of connections of the same source IP address and the destination port number.
- Number of connections of the same destination IP address and the source port number.
- Number of connections of the same source IP address and the destination IP address.

The rest of the variables are related to basic features, content features, time features, and additional generated features of the network. The variables were obtained from the UNSW-NB15 feature file (UNSW-NB15_features.csv).

AN INTRODUCTION TO LINEAR DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS

Introduction

This study employs the Linear Discriminant Analysis to design the Intrusion Detection System (LDA). The LDA is a dimensionality reduction statistical method most frequently used in the supervised learning process in modeling differences in groups by separating two or more classes. LDA achieves this objective by evaluating an optimal linear transformation that maximizes the between-class variance and minimizing within class variance, thus achieving maximum class discrimination.

Basic assumptions in Linear Discriminant Analysis

- Each variable (feature) in the dataset is normally distributed.
- Constancy of variance is assumed for each variable (feature).

Steps involved in the Fisher's Linear Discriminant Analysis procedure

1) Calculate the between class variance, the distance between the mean of different classes using the following equation,

$$S_b = \sum_{i=1}^g N_i (\mu_i - \mu) (\mu_i - \mu)'$$

Where, g is the number of classes, S_b is the between class scatter matrix, N_i is the vector of number of items in class i , μ is the Mean vector of the data and μ_i is the Mean vector of the class i

2) Calculate the scatter of features around mean of each class which is called within class variance using the equation,

$$S_w = \sum_{i=1}^g \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} (x_{ij} - \mu_i) (x_{ij} - \mu_i)'$$

3) Maximize in between-class variance S_b while minimizing within class variance S_w . Alternatively, maximize the ratio,

$$LDA = \text{Det}(S_b) / \text{Det}(S_w)$$

This ratio is maximized when the column vectors of the projection matrix are the eigen vectors of $S_w^{-1} S_b$.¹⁶

Methodology and results

My current study has used R software Version 3.6.1 to read and organize the data as per requirement. Subsequently, library (MASS) package was used for Linear Discriminant Analysis of the data to discriminate various attack categories and to assess the efficiency of the models. The output was used to calculate the various metrics to assess the overall efficiency of the model.

The linear discriminant analysis to design an intrusion detection system in my research was carried out in two stages. The first model used only the connection features to predict the intrusions while the second model used 12 relevant features belong to basic features, content features, time features, and additional generated features for the analysis. The intrusion data in training data set is as follows:

The highest number of records are in the Normal category with 56000 records followed by Generic, Exploits, and Fuzzers categories with 40000, 33393 and 18184 records respectively. The other categories DoS, Reconnaissance, and Analysis have 12264, 10491, and 2000 respectively. The categories Back doors, Shell Code, and Worms have a smaller number of records as compared to other categories with records 1764, 1133 and 130 respectively.

Model-1 (Predictor variables correspond to connection characteristics in the training data set)

Table-1: Results from the training data set for Model-1

	Analysis	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Normal	Reconnaissance	Shellcode	Worms
Analysis	0	0	0	1629	0	19	352	0	0	0
Backdoor	0	0	3	1431	0	10	302	0	0	0
DoS	0	0	23	10486	6	114	1635	0	0	0
Exploits	0	0	93	28307	19	199	4775	0	0	0
Fuzzers	0	0	21	8563	28	29	9543	0	0	0
Generic	0	0	3	1827	36	36484	1650	0	0	0
Normal	0	0	16	13697	133	245	41909	0	0	0
Reconnaissance	0	0	43	7704	1	19	2724	0	0	0
Shellcode	0	0	0	724	0	0	409	0	0	0
Worms	0	0	0	105	0	0	25	0	0	0

Table-2: Predicting power of the model-1 (in Percentages)

Analysis	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Normal	Reconnaissance	Shell Code	Worms
0	0	0.18	84.77	0.15	91.21	74.84	0	0	0

The model-1 predicts 78.84% of Normal network flow categories correctly. It also predicts 91.21% of Generic category, and 84.77% of Exploit category correctly while provides us with poor prediction of DoS attacks (0.18%) and Fuzzers (0.15%) while its prediction power is very poor in case of Analysis, Backdoor, Reconnaissance, Shell code, and worms attack categories. The results are shown in Table-1 and Table-2

Table-3: Confusion Matrix-1 for Model-1

Class	Predicted Normal	Predicted Attack	Total
Actual Normal	True Negative = TN = 41,909	False Positive = FP = 14,091	TN+FP = 56,000
Actual Attack	False Negative = FN = 21,415	True Positive = TP = 97,926	FN+TP = 119,341

Model-2 (Predictor variables correspond to non-network features)

The model-2 predicts 54.66% of Normal network flow categories correctly. It also predicts 99.07% of Generic category, 27.97% of Exploit category and 10.10% of Fuzzers category correctly while it provides us with poor prediction of DoS attacks (0.04%) while its prediction power is very poor in case of Analysis, Backdoor, Reconnaissance, Shell code, and worms attack categories. The results and the predicting power for model-2 are shown in Table-4 and Table-5.

Results from the modeling of UNSW-NB15 training data set that correspond to Model-2 with predictor variables as basic features, content features, time features, and additional generated features of the network are as follows:

Table-4: Results from the test data set for Model-2

	Analysis	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Normal	Reconnaissance	Shellcode	Worms
Analysis	270	3	4	295	30	1392	2	1	1	2
Backdoor	8	0	0	115	63	1559	1	0	0	0
DoS	51	3	6	1371	383	10287	157	5	1	0
Exploits	220	4	4	9341	691	20849	2250	5	4	025
Fuzzers	130	0	0	1173	1836	14902	143	0	0	0
Generic	10	0	1	224	53	39629	76	0	2	5
Normal	359	3	7	5318	844	18817	30607	1	6	38
Reconnaissance	43	0	0	1488	88	8863	9	0	0	0
Shellcode	0	0	0	1	28	1099	5	0	0	0
Worms	10	0	0	77	4	20	19	0	0	0

Table-5: Predicting power of the model-2 (in Percentages)

Analysis	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Normal	Reconnaissance	Shell Code	Worms
0	0	0.04	27.97	10.10	99.07	54.66	0	0	0

Table-6: Confusion Matrix-2 for Model-2

Class	Predicted Normal	Predicted Attack	Total
Actual Normal	True Negative = TN = 30,607	False Positive = FP = 25,393	TN+FP = 56,000
Actual Attack	False Negative = FN = 2,662	True Positive = TP = 116,679	FN+TP = 119,341

Model-3 (Predictor variables correspond to connection features in the test data set)

The test data set of UNSW-NB15 has the highest number of records are in the Normal category with 37000 records followed by Generic, Exploits, and Fuzzers categories with 18871, 11132 and 6062 records respectively. The other categories DoS, Reconnaissance, and Analysis have 4089, 3496, and 677 respectively. The categories Back doors, Shell Code, and Worms have a smaller number of records as compared to other categories with records 583, 378 and 44 respectively.

Table-7: Results from the test data set for Model-3

	Analysis	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Normal	Reconnaissance	Shellcode	Worms
Analysis	4	8	7	0	36	127	494	1	0	0
Backdoor	4	8	0	0	36	127	407	1	0	0
DoS	4	8	186	0	39	201	3644	7	0	0
Exploits	8	16	187	3	93	305	10508	12	0	0
Fuzzers	8	38	21	0	194	310	5490	1	0	0
Generic	0	24	13	2	543	11231	7058	0	0	0
Normal	5	13	447	33	188	31	36283	0	0	0
Reconnaissance	0	0	39	8	2	11	3434	2	0	0
Shellcode	0	0	0	0	2	0	376	0	0	0
Worms	0	0	1	0	0	0	43	0	0	0

Table-8: Predicting power of the model-3 (in Percentages)

Analysis	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Normal	Reconnaissance	Shell Code	Worms
0.50	1.37	4.55	0.03	3.20	59.51	98.06	0.06	0	0

The model-3 is able to predict 98.06% of Normal network flow categories correctly. It also predicts 59.51% of Generic category, 4.55% of Denial-of-service attack categories with certainty while provides us with poor prediction of Backdoor attacks (1.37%) and Fuzzers (3.20%) while its prediction power is very poor in case of Analysis, Exploits, Reconnaissance, Shell code, and worms attack categories. The results are shown in Table-7 and Table-8.

Table-9: Confusion Matrix for Model-3

Class	Predicted Normal	Predicted Attack	Total
Actual Normal	True Negative = TN = 36,283	False Positive = FP = 717	TN+FP = 37,000
Actual Attack	False Negative = FN = 31,454	True Positive = TP = 13,878	FN+TP = 45,332

Model-4 (Predictor variables correspond to non-connection features of test data set)

The Model-4 have used UNSW-NB15 test data set with predictor variables correspond to basic features, content features, time features, and additional generated features of the network.

Table-10: Results from test data set for Model-4

	Analysis	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Normal	Reconnaissance	Shellcode	Worms
Analysis	0	0	0	0	1	29	647	0	0	0
Backdoor	0	0	0	0	6	21	556	0	0	0
DoS	4	3	18	21	68	156	3816	2	0	1
Exploits	5	4	17	317	91	212	10456	1	1	28
Fuzzers	1	1	39	8	195	464	5353	0	1	0
Generic	0	0	6	1	2	634	18227	0	0	1
Normal	14	0	85	367	217	1430	34595	1	4	287
Reconnaissance	0	0	0	0	15	61	3420	0	0	0
Shellcode	0	0	1	0	0	28	349	0	0	0
Worms	0	0	0	0	0	2	42	0	0	0

Table-11: Predicting power of the model-4 (in Percentages)

Analysis	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Normal	Reconnaissance	Shell Code	Worms
0	0	0.44	2.8	3.2	3.36	93.5	0	0	0

The model-4 is able to predict 93.5% of Normal network flow correctly. It also predicts 3.36% of Generic category, 0.44% of Denial-of-service attack categories, 3.2% of Fuzzers, and 2.8% of Exploits with certainty while its prediction power is very poor in other categories. The results are shown in Table-10 and Table-11.

Table-12: Confusion Matrix-4 for Model-4

Class	Predicted Normal	Predicted Attack	Total
Actual Normal	True Negative = TN = 34,595	False Positive = FP = 2,405	TN+FP = 37,000
Actual Attack	False Negative = FN = 42,866	True Positive = TP = 2,466	FN+TP = 45,332

Performance Measures from Confusion Matrices

Table-13: Measuring metrics for the models that have used only the connection features

Measure	Formula	Model-1 (Trained Data)	Model-3 (Test Data)
True Positive Rate (TPR)	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN} = \frac{\text{Correct Intrusions}}{\text{Intrusions}}$	0.8206 (82.06%)	0.3061 (30.61%)
False Positive Rate (FPR)	$\frac{FP}{TN + FP} = \frac{\text{Normal as intrusions}}{\text{Normal}}$	0.2516 (25.16%)	0.0194 (1.94%)
True Negative Rate (TNR)	$\frac{TN}{TN + FP} = \frac{\text{Correct Normal}}{\text{Normal}}$	0.7484 (74.84%)	0.9806 (98.06%)
False Negative Rate (FNR)	$\frac{FN}{TP + FN} = \frac{\text{Intrusions as Normal}}{\text{Intrusions}}$	0.1794 (17.94%)	0.6939 (69.39%)
Accuracy (A)	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN} = \frac{\text{Correct Classifications}}{\text{All Instances}}$	0.7975 (79.75%)	0.6093 (60.93%)
Precision (or) Detection Rate	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP} = \frac{\text{Correct Intrusions}}{\text{Instances as Intrusions}}$	0.8742 (87.42%)	0.9509 (95.09%)

Table-14: Measuring metrics for models that have used the non-connection features

Measure	Formula	Model-2 (Trained Data)	Model-4 (Test Data)
True Positive Rate (TPR)	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN} = \frac{\text{Correct Intrusions}}{\text{Intrusions}}$	0.9777 (97.77%)	0.0544 (5.44%)
False Positive Rate (FPR)	$\frac{FP}{TN + FP} = \frac{\text{Normal as intrusions}}{\text{Normal}}$	0.4534 (45.34%)	0.0650 (6.50%)
True Negative Rate (TNR)	$\frac{TN}{TN + FP} = \frac{\text{Correct Normal}}{\text{Normal}}$	0.5466 (54.66%)	0.9350 (93.50%)
False Negative Rate (FNR)	$\frac{FN}{TP + FN} = \frac{\text{Intrusions as Normal}}{\text{Intrusions}}$	0.0223 (2.23%)	0.9460 (94.60%)
Accuracy (A)	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN} = \frac{\text{Correct Classifications}}{\text{All Instances}}$	0.8400 (84.00%)	0.4501 (45.01%)
Precision (or) Detection Rate	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP} = \frac{\text{Correct Intrusions}}{\text{Instances as Intrusions}}$	0.8213 (82.13%)	0.5063 (50.63%)

The measuring metrics for Model-1 and Model-3 that have used only network features are deduced using the confusion matrices shown in Table-3 and Table-9. The Table-13 shown above summarizes various performance measures of Model-1 and Model-3. The measuring metrics for Model-2 and Model-4 that have used only non-network features are deduced using confusion matrices shown in Table-6 and Table-12. The Table-14 shown above summarizes various performance measures for Model-2 and Model-4.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Many earlier research works have used different datasets and different methods to design intrusion detection system with an effort to achieve better accuracy and detection rate ^{17,18,19,20,21,22}. My study has used linear discriminant analysis in the design of intrusion detection system using multi-class modelling employing both trained data set and test data set for connection features and non-connection features.

The Model-1 (Table-1) and the Model-3 (Table-7) have used only the connection features to build the Intrusion Detection Model. The model for training data set is able to predict the intrusion detection with an accuracy of 79.75% and a detection rate of 87.42%, a balanced prediction in both trained data set and test data set (Table-13). The test data set predicts intrusion with an accuracy of 60.93% and a detection rate of 95.09% consistent with the results from the training data set (Table-13). However, this result slightly differs from earlier works on intrusion detection systems where the accuracy rates were 71.34 and 86.74 and detection rates were 73.07 and 85.27 respectively ^{23,24}. The difference in the results may be due to the difference in the use of data sets or in the choice of methodology of these earlier works.

The model-2 (Table-4) and Model-4 (Table-10) have used basic features, content features, time features, and additional generated features of the network to build the intrusion detection model. The model for the training dataset has intrusion detection with an accuracy 84% and detection rate 82.13%. The model for the test dataset predicts of intrusions with an accuracy of 45.01% and detection rate 50.63%. In this case, model from the trained data set has better prediction as compared to the model from the test dataset. The better results in the trained dataset may be ascribed to the balanced number of records in the intrusion categories.

Now, one shall compare model that have used the connection features (Model-1) and the model that used other related features of the network (Model-2). While we compare the results from Model-1 (Table-1) and Model-2 (Table-4) for the trained dataset one can observe that the model that used connection features (Model-1) provide us with far better results as compared to the model that used other related network features (Model-2) with true negative rates (TNR) 74.84% and 54.66%, detection rates 87.42% and 82.13%. However, accuracy in the prediction is slightly better with the Model-2 as compared to Model-1 with accuracies 79.75% and 84% respectively. A far better results are seen in case of test data set that used connection features (Model-3) and other network features (Model-4) with true negative rates (TNR) 98.06% and 93.50%, accuracies 60.93% and 45.01%, and detection rates 95.09% and 50.63%, respectively. The results indicate that network features are better suited to detect cyber intrusions as compared to the other network features. This result is in accordance with a review on intrusion detection systems that concluded that the network features are best suited in identifying the intrusions ²⁵.

CONCLUSION

There have been many earlier works on intrusion detection systems using various network features and using different datasets. However, as far as I know, none of these earlier works have made an effort to build an intrusion detection model using Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) with UNSW-NB15 dataset employing network features and non-network features. This current research has used both the sets of features and identified that the network features play an important role in the network intrusion detection rather than the non-network features. This factor makes our work to stand apart from those earlier research works on designing intrusion detection systems.

SIGNIFICANCE STATEMENT

My current study also offers scope for further research in designing intrusion detection systems. The study can be extended to build intrusion detection systems for individual intrusion categories such as Analysis, Backdoor, Denial of Service, Exploits, Fuzzers, Generic, Reconnaissance, Shell-code, and Worms. The study shall also be extended to frame intrusion detection systems for each of distinct internet services and protocols. Besides, the results from our study reveals that a balanced training dataset and test dataset, will further improve the efficiency of the design of intrusion detection systems. Though, attempts to build intrusion detection systems in these directions were not made, it can be reserved to further intrusion detection research in the near future.

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Contribution by the author

The author is the only contributor of this research work.

Conflicts of interest

Being the only contributor of this research work the author declares no potential conflict of interest.

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